

Vegetation dataset of Land Use/Land Cover and Leaf Area Index

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D1.1 Vegetation dataset of Land Use/Land Cover and Leaf Area Index

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CONFESS

Consistent representation of temporal variations of boundary forcing in reanalyses and seasonal forecasts

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Acronyms

Acronym	Description
AVHRR	Advanced Very-High-Resolution Radiometer
BATS	Biosphere-Atmosphere Transfer Scheme classification
C3S	Copernicus Climate Change Service
CCI	climate change initiative
CDF	cumulative distribution function
CGLS	Copernicus Global Land Services
CNES	Centre National d'Etudes Spatiales (French Space Agency)
CREAF	Centre de Recerca Ecològica i Aplicacions Forestals
CVH	cover of high vegetations
CVL	cover of low vegetations
ECMWF	European Centre for Medium range Weather Forecasts
ESA	European Space Agency
IFS	Integrated Forecasting System
INRA	Institut national de la recherche agronomique
LAI	Leaf Area index
LU/LC	land use/land cover
MERIS	Medium Resolution Imaging Spectrometer
NOAA	National Oceanic and Atmospheric Administration
PFT	Plant functional type
PROBA-V	Vegetation instrument on board of PROBA satellite
SPOT	Système Pour l'Observation de la Terre
VEGETATION	VEGETATION sensor onboard SPOT4/5
THEIA	Theia Land Data Centre
TVH	types of high vegetations
TVL	types of low vegetations
UNLCCS	United Nations Land Cover Classification System

1. Executive Summary

The Vegetation dataset of land use/land cover (LU/LC) and Leaf Area index (LAI) are essential for the CONFESS project. One of the main targets of this project is improving the usability of the information delivered across different Copernicus Services within the land-atmosphere coupled system. It aims at using new Earth Observations of LU/LC and vegetation states and the impact of their inter-annual variability on reanalysis and seasonal forecast.

CONFESS uses the LU/LC and LAI data from the Copernicus Climate Change Service (C3S) and the Copernicus Global Land Services (CGLS) for the period from 1993 to 2019. The LU/LC data is provided at a yearly frequency and adapted to the BATS classification (Biosphere-Atmosphere Transfer Scheme classification) as used within the ECMWF Integrated Forecasting System (IFS). While the LAI data provided every 10-days, is extended from the 1999 to 1993 with the AVHRR-based data available through the C3S and interpolated to 1km spatial resolution. The harmonisation of the LAI data from the two data sources is assured with a CDF matching procedure.

2. Introduction

2.1 Background

An essential element for assessing the impact of the vegetation inter-annual variability on reanalysis and seasonal forecast is the availability of observed data that could constrain model simulations. This task will produce long-term gap free and harmonized land data sets for the period of 1993-2019 related to the land cover, the vegetation status and its variability with the purpose of being used in land reanalysis and seasonal forecast simulations. The considered data sets are the land cover (LC) describing the type of surface (forests, grassland, cropland, inland-water) and the vegetation status expressed by the Leaf Area Index (LAI).

The interconsistency of the land dataset in uncoupled land simulations and coupled model integrations will be facilitated by the data collected in the C3S and the CGLS at a native high spatial resolution enabling to intercompare and interpolate consistently all the fields to a target resolution.

2.2 Scope of this deliverable

2.2.1 Objectives of this deliverable

This deliverable defines the vegetation dataset to be used in the land reanalysis and seasonal forecast simulations and describes their generation procedure.

2.2.2 Work performed in this deliverable.

The LU/LC data was translated to the IFS BATS classification and processed from the native resolution to the target simulation resolution for 1993-2019

The LAI data from CGLS, THEIA and C3S was harmonised for the period 1993-2019 at 1km resolution then disaggregated into high and low vegetation components along with an aggregation to the target simulation resolutions.

2.2.3 Deviations and counter measures

The CGLS LAI v2 (GEOV2) data was found to have a temporal inconsistency between the SPOT-VEGETATION (1999-2013) and PROBA-V (2013-2019) periods. An additional harmonization procedure is applied between these two periods.

The C3S AVHRR-based LAI data was found to be not gap-filled and its production procedure slightly different from the CGLS v2 (GEOV2) data. An alternative source of data which has the same production procedure as the CGLS GEOV2 is used, this data is the AVHRR-GEOV2 provided through the THEIA platform. The following is an acknowledgement for the use of these data:

“The GEOV2/AVHRR product was generated by CNES in the framework of the Theia land data centre, a French national inter-agency organization. The GEOV2/AVHRR algorithm was developed by CREAM and INRA. The research leading to the current version of the product has received initial funding from various European Commission Research and Technical Development programs. The product is based on AVHRR 1km data (© NOAA) and is distributed by Theia.”

3. Land Use/ Land cover data

3.1 Original data description

The native data used for LU/LC is the ESA-CCI LC data brokered through the C3S CDS. The global C3S LU/LC data is provided at 300m spatial resolution for 1993 to 2019 and are based on the AVHRR, SPOT-VEGETATION, MERIS and PROBA-V satellite and are made consistent throughout the whole 1993-2019 period. A detailed description of the original data is available at <https://cds.climate.copernicus.eu/cdsapp#!/dataset/satellite-land-cover?tab=doc>.

3.2 Data processing

The ESA-CCI data processing is performed in three parts:

1. Aggregation of ESA-CCI land cover classes from 300m to the target resolution:

All pixels at 300m are aggregated to the nearest target resolution grid point generating a fractional cover for each of the ESA-CCI land cover classes.

2. Conversion to the IFS vegetation types:

The output of the target resolution aggregated data from previous step is then loaded and a cross-walking table (Table 1) is applied transforming the fraction cover of each of ESA-CCI land cover classes into fraction cover of the IFS BATS vegetation types.

Figure 1: Bare-ground cover difference between CCI-LC maps with the adopted cross-walking table - the first version cross-walking table based on the 2015 maps.

The choice of the cross-walking table is crucial for a correct PFT classification, as no unique solution is available and it would strongly drive the PFT distribution and therefore the energy, water and carbon cycles. In this case a first version guided by the United Nations Land Cover Classification System (UNLCCS) is performed. This first version is then evaluated with the land surface model output which pointed to an overestimation of the bare-ground cover (Figure 1). Based on these results, a revised version of the cross-walking table (Table 1) is adopted after further guidance from member of the CCI-LC expert team.

3. Consistency with the land sea mask

For the target resolution final product, a consistency with the land sea mask is ensured by setting all points where the input land sea mask indicates water ($lsm \leq 0.5$) to 0.

Table 1: Cross walking table used to convert the ESA-CCI types (http://maps.elie.ucl.ac.be/CCI/viewer/download/CCI-LC_Maps_Legend.pdf) into the BATS vegetations types.

ESACCI INDEX	IFS NAME	crops	short grass	everg needle	deci needle	deci broad	everg broad	tall grass	desert	tundra	irri crops	semi-desert	ice caps	bogs marshes	inland water	ocean	ever shrubs	deci shrubs	mix forest	interrupted forest	water and land mix
		IFS INDEX	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12	13	14	15	16	17	18	19
	IFS HILO	L	L	H	H	H	H	L	N.A	L	L	L	N.A	L	N.A	N.A	L	L	H	H	L
0									100												
10		90	10																		
11		90	10																		
12		30																70			
20		90	10																		
30		60	15			5	5										10	5			
40		20	30			7.5	7.5										20	15			
50							90										5	5			
60			30			50												20			
61			15			70												15			
62			45			30			0									25			
70			15	70													10	5			
71			15	70													10	5			
72			45	30					0								25	0			
80			30		50												5	15			
81			15		70												5	10			
82			45		30				0								0	25			
90			25	20	10	30			0								10	5			
100			40	5	5	20	10										10	10			
110			60	5		10	5										10	10			

120			30															20	50					
121			30															70						
122			30																70					
130			100						0															
140										100														
150			30	5		5	0		50									5	5					
151			30	10		10			50															
152			30						50									10	10					
153			50						50															
160			25			37.5	37.5																	
170							75												25					
180			10											80				5	5					
190			20	2.5		2.5			75															
200									100															
201									100															
202									100															
210																	100							
220														100										

3.3 Processed LU/LC data files description

The LU/LC products are generated at the reduced gaussian octahedral grids Tco319 (36km), Tco199 (64km) and the reduced gaussian linear grid TL255 (80km) resolutions for the period 1993 – 2019 with a yearly frequency.

For each year and each resolution 4 grib files are generated:

TVL, TVH: contain the types of low and high vegetations respectively.

And CVL, CVH: contain the cover fraction of low and high vegetations respectively.

For illustrative purpose, and to show the time evolution of the LU/LC, Figure 2 shows the maps the vegetation types for years 2000 and 2019. The differences in term of types are very minor and localised. However, in Figure 3, the vegetation cover differences between 2000 and 2019 shows more clear signals especially the change from forest to low vegetation cover such as in the eastern part of the Amazon and the eastern Siberian regions.

Figure 2: Vegetation types for 2000 (left) and 2019 (right), high vegetation types are in upper panels and low vegetation types are in lower panels.

Figure 3: Vegetation cover differences between 2000 minus 2019 (right) for low vegetation and (left) for high vegetation covers.

4. Leaf Area Index data

4.1 Original LAI data description

The original LAI data is from the Copernicus global land services (CGLS) global LAI Version 2 data (GEOV2) hereafter named as CGLS GEOV2. This Version 2 product is generated at 1km spatial resolution from Collection 3 of SPOT/VEGETATION data, from 1999-2014, from Collection 0 of PROBA-V data for 2014 to 2016 and from Collection 1 of PROBA-V data for 2017 to 2019. Additionally, for the back period from 1993 to 1999, LAI data based on the AVHRR sensor brokered through the Copernicus climate services (C3S) named as C3S-AVHRR is explored. AVHRR LAI data based on the same processing chain as the CGLS GEOV2 and brokered through THEIA Land Data Centre at 0.05 degree spatial resolution is also used, named hereafter AVHRR-GEOV2.

Detailed descriptions of the original data is available at:

<https://cds.climate.copernicus.eu/cdsapp#!/dataset/satellite-lai-fapar?tab=doc> ;

https://land.copernicus.eu/global/sites/cgls.vito.be/files/products/CGLOPS1_PUM_LAI1km-V2_I1.33.pdf and

<https://theia.sedoo.fr/wp-content-theia/uploads/sites/2/2020/11/THEIA-MU-44-0369-CNES-GEOV2-AVHRR-Product-User-Manual-V2.pdf>

4.2 Harmonisation of the LAI data

In order to get the full timeseries of the LAI data at high resolution, different products are used. The chosen reference product for CONFESS is the CGLS LAI v2 (CGLS GEOV2) data which is provided globally at 1km resolution and spans the period from 1999 to 2019. This product is also of interest because its follow-up data that uses the same processing algorithm is provided operationally in near-real-time.

The last period of the CGLS GEOV2 data (2014-2019) corresponds to a different sensor (PROBA-V) than the first period (1999-2013) which was acquired by the SPOT-VEGETATION sensor. A systematic shift (bias) is discovered between these two periods and a correction is applied to ensure a temporal consistency between them. A cumulative distribution function matching correction method (CDF matching) that conserves the mean and the variance of the data is chosen as the shift is systematic and uniform across the period (Figure 4) although the timeseries is not extensive.

$$lai_{PROBAV_{new}} = \alpha lai_{PROBAV_{orig}} + \beta \quad \text{where,}$$

$$\alpha = \frac{\sigma_{lai_{SPOT}}}{\sigma_{lai_{PROBAV}}}, \quad \beta = \overline{lai_{SPOT}} - \alpha \overline{lai_{PROBAV}}$$

\overline{lai} , σ_{lai} being the LAI mean and standard deviation.

Figure 4: Leaf Area Index global mean from CGLS GEOV2 time series (1993-2019) A shift is detected from the beginning of 2014 corresponding to the change of the sensor to PROBA-V (green line) and the corrected data with CDF matching (dotted red).

As stated in section 4.1, the back period from 1993 to 1999 is provided from the AVHRR-GEOV2 data globally at 0.05degree resolution.

A conservative interpolation is firstly applied to this data to convert it at similar resolution as the CGLS GEOV2 data(1km), this will ensure a benefit from the high-resolution details when harmonising it with the CGLS GEOV2 data.

A CDF matching method is then applied on the 1km AVHRR-GEOV2 interpolated data to ensure the consistency of the LAI data over of the full 1993-2019 (actually 1982-2019) period between CGLS-GEOV2 and AVHRR-GEOV2 data without affecting the trend or the inter-annual variability.

Figure 5: Leaf Area Index global mean from CGLS GEOV2 time series (solid red), CGLS GEOV2 CDF corrected (dashed red), C3S AVHRR (solid blue), AVHRR GEOV2 (dashed green) and AVHRR GEOV2 CDF corrected (solid grey).

The data harmonization based subsequently on conservative interpolation and CDF matching results in a consistent long time series that covers the period 1982 to 2019 (Figure 5). The data shows its ability to monitor and detect anomalous years such as the 2018 drought over Europe as depicted in Figure 6 where the 2017 LAI can be larger than the 2018 LAI by 4 [m^2/m^2].

Figure 6: Leaf Area Index global difference (2017 minus 2018) showing the drought related anomaly over Europe (green).

4.3 Processing and disaggregation of the LAI data

The 1km harmonised LAI data spanning the period between 1993-2019 is available to be used by the project partners according to their model need.

For the ECMWF IFS model the LAI data is disaggregated into low and high vegetation components and the processing is done in 2 main steps:

1. The 1 km LAI is aggregated to the target grid along with a disaggregation into low and high vegetation.

Each 1km pixel of the harmonized LAI (lai_{hr}) is aggregated to the target grid total LAI (lai) and lai_{lv} and lai_{hv} are derived considering the low vegetation fraction (cvl), high vegetation fraction (cvh) and land sea mask (lsm). cvl , cvh and lsm are derived from aggregated 300m ESA-CCI land cover data (section 3). The aggregated lai , lai_{lv} , lai_{hv} for a particular target grid cell considers all 1km pixels falling inside that grid cell ($i=1, n$ pixels where $lsm > 0.5$). Each 1km pixel is assigned to high or low vegetation depending on cvh , cvl and a weighted average on cvh or cvl is taken to derive the low and high vegetation lai :

$$\begin{aligned}
 lai &= \frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n laihr_i \\
 lai_{lv} &= \frac{1}{W} \sum_{i=1}^n w_i \times laihr_i \quad W = \sum_{i=1}^n w_i; w_i = \begin{cases} cvl_i & cvl_i > cvh_i \\ 0 & cvl_i \leq cvh_i \end{cases} \\
 lai_{hv} &= \frac{1}{W} \sum_{i=1}^n w_i \times laihr_i \quad W = \sum_{i=1}^n w_i; w_i = \begin{cases} cvh_i & cvh_i > cvl_i \\ 0 & cvh_i \leq cvl_i \end{cases}
 \end{aligned}$$

2. The disaggregated low and high LAI is further processed for consistency with the land cover map and to conserve total original LAI product.

The low and high vegetation *lai* for each vegetation type are scaled to guarantee consistency in terms of the annual maximum. For each vegetation type the maximum annual *lai* is computed lai_{vty_max} and the median of the distribution is taken as representative for that vegetation type $lai_{vty_max_med}$. A new *lai* is computed by scaling the maximum *lai* in each grid-cell with the $lai_{vty_max_med}$ weighted by the vegetation fraction (*cv*, which is *cvl* or *cvh* depending on the type of vegetation):

$$\begin{aligned}
 lai_{vty_max} &= \max(lai_{vty}) \\
 lai_{vty_max_med} &= \text{median}(lai_{vty_max}) \\
 \alpha &= \min(5, \max(0.2, \frac{lai_{vty_max_med}}{lai_{vty_max}}))) \\
 lai_{vty} &= (1 - cv) \times \alpha \times lai_{vty} + cv \times lai_{vty}
 \end{aligned}$$

Finally, the updated *lai_{lv}* and *lai_{hv}* for each date are scaled to conserve the total *lai*:

$$\begin{aligned}
 lai^* &= \frac{cvl \times lai_{lv} + cvh \times lai_{hv}}{cvl + cvh} \\
 \beta &= \min(5, \max(0.2, \frac{lai}{lai^*})) \\
 lai_{lv} &= \beta \times lai_{lv} \\
 lai_{hv} &= \beta \times lai_{hv}
 \end{aligned}$$

4.4 LAI data files description

The LAI products are generated at the reduced gaussian octahedral grids Tco319 (36km), Tco199 (64km) and the reduced gaussian linear grid TL255 (80km) resolutions for the period 1993 – 2019 with a monthly frequency.

For each year and each resolution 2 grib files are generated:

month_lail: contains low vegetation LAI global fields for the 12 months of the year.

month_laih: contains high vegetation LAI global fields for the 12 months of the year.

Additionally, 36 netcdf files/year of the harmonised 1993-2019 1km total LAI data is provided for each 10-daily period of the year with mid-period timestamp on the 5th, 15th and 25th of each month.

5. Conclusion

This deliverable provided the land use/land cover data based on the ESA-CCI/C3S for the period of 1993 to 2019. The LAI data for the same period was also provided based on harmonization of the CGLS/C3S data and the AVHRR based data. These data will be made available for the community and will be prescribed into the offline and coupled model to assess the impact of their inter-annual variability on reanalysis and seasonal forecast.

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